

DEVELOPING THE CREATIVE SKILLS OF PRE-SCHOOL CHILDREN IN THE PROCESS OF ACTIVITIES

Matchanova Nazokat

Independent researcher of Urganch State University
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10158083>

Abstract: In this thesis, there are opinions about the theoretical foundations of the development of creative thinking abilities through activities performed with children of preschool age.

Key words: Education, upbringing, thinking, student, creative, methodology, talented person, activity, flexibility of thinking, communication, modeling.

Pre-school education provides a healthy, all-round development of a child, instills in him a desire to study, prepares him for regular education. Preschool education is carried out in the family, as well as in state and non-state (non-state) preschool education organizations until the child reaches 6-7 years of age. The main tasks of preschool education are defined as:

- ❖ educating children intellectually, spiritually and morally based on the rich national, cultural and historical heritage of the nation and universal values;
- ❖ formation of national pride and patriotism in children;
- ❖ forming the need for education in children of preschool age, the desire to study, and preparing them for the regular educational process;
- ❖ development of children's thinking, formation of skills of independent and free expression of one's opinion.
- ❖ aims to ensure children's physical and mental health.

Children of the same age, as well as children of different ages, can be admitted to groups of preschool and preschool children of preschool educational organizations. Pre-school educational organizations are organized taking into account the demographic, socio-economic and other characteristics of the regions. Pre-school educational organizations are established and terminated in accordance with the Law. Preschool educational organizations are divided into the following types according to their directions:

- state pre-school education organizations;
- non-state preschool educational organizations;
- joint preschool educational organizations;
- multidisciplinary specialized pre-school educational organizations.

Kinds of preschool education organizations are chosen by parents. The procedure for admission of children to preschool education organizations, their transfer from one institution to another, and their expulsion from the institution is determined by the procedure established by the Ministry of Preschool Education in state institutions, and in non-state preschool education organizations, it is determined by the organization's Charter.

As in every field, in the system of pre-school education organizations, persons with relevant education, professional training and high moral qualities have the right to engage in pedagogical activities. Training, retraining and upgrading of pedagogical personnel, maintaining the quality of the profession at a competitive level is ensured by state bodies responsible for education management. The educational and pedagogical tasks of the pedagogical personnel of preschool educational organizations are determined by the Ministry of Preschool Education based on the state requirements for the type of preschool educational organizations.

It provides conditions for the introduction of advanced pedagogical and information technologies, new programs recommended by experts, methodical manuals, and didactic materials. Mutual relations of pedagogical personnel are seen on the basis of pedagogy of cooperation, democracy, respect, recognition of the individual's own value. Based on the state requirements for the education of preschool children, support programs are presented in order to provide comprehensive education to preschool children. These basic programs allow to develop more than 3 million children who are currently not involved in preschool educational institutions and to prepare them for school based on the requirements of the unified state. At the end of the educational process, the main goal was to bring up an independent, free, educated, in a word, well-rounded person. This first type of continuous education system required a unique approach to preschool education.

From the day a child is born, it is the responsibility of the state, society, and parents to raise him healthy, intelligent, and well-behaved. Children's mental activity was first implemented through treatment, then through educational activities, games and other activities. The child is always among objects and events. He is always familiar with something, learns something, holds something, listens to something, this is how the child understands the world. Tevarakatrophe items and objects affect the children's sensory organs, analyzers, and intuition is formed. Intuition helps to learn certain properties in children. Development of mental skills and abilities in a child, examination of the

subjects of the simplest activity methods, distinguishing important and non-important signs in them and comparing them with other subjects is one of the tasks of mental education in children of preschool age. These skills and abilities are components of cognitive activity and help the child acquire knowledge in depth. The science of pedagogy and psychology puts forward the opinion that to effectively solve the tasks of mental education, first of all, the correct use of the child's capabilities, and secondly, there should be no excessive stress that causes the child's organism to tire. Full mental development takes place only in the process of properly organized activities. For this reason, the task of pedagogues is to create the necessary conditions to have an educational effect, first through treatment, then through educational activities and other activities.

The role of mental education in preparing children for school education is great. It serves as a resource for children to acquire knowledge, to develop their mental activity, to acquire mental skills and abilities, to study successfully at school, and to prepare for future work. The main tasks of mental education of preschool children are as follows:

Forming a scientific view of the system of knowledge about nature and society in children. The child should have a clear idea about the surrounding things, their function, quality, properties, what materials they use, and how they are made. Development of mental processes related to cognition: intuition, perception, memory, imagination, thinking, speech, etc. Developing speech about knowledge is a free task of intellectual education. Interest in learning and development of mental abilities, mental work culture. The task of intellectual education is to develop children's curiosity, to develop their intelligence, and on this basis to create an interest in learning.

Development of mental skills and abilities, that is, simple methods of activity, examination of objects, distinguishing important and unimportant signs in them, comparing them with other objects is one of the tasks of mental education of preschool children. After systematic training on getting to know plants and animals, children will have a certain idea about plants and young animals. Then, in order to develop children's intellectual skills and abilities, it is possible to plan educational activities with educational games.

These are: "You define, I find." Didactic task: to answer the questions of adults by distinguishing the characteristic sign of an object and naming it. Game action: Tell the adults a riddle. The rule of the game: It is impossible to say the name of the thing being described. Answer the teacher's questions clearly and

correctly. Arrangement: Vegetables and fruits are placed on the table. The teacher's chair is placed so that the plants are not visible.

The course of the game: The educator chooses one of the vegetables on the table for the children. I will ask you how it is. You answer. Just don't say his name. I will try to find it from your answers. Then the educator asks questions in order: "What is its shape? Is it round like a ball on all sides? Does it have a hole? What is its color?" etc. Children answer the questions in full. After the children tell about the characteristic features of the object, the teacher finds the riddle. In educational activities, games, work in the nature corner and on the playground, during excursions and walks, the educator shows children the diversity and beauty of the world around them, introduces them to various features and qualities of plants, and forms an elementary understanding of the world of plants and animals. . The attractive attitude of children allows to learn more actively from the teacher's story. In educational activities and didactic games, the child learns to distinguish, compare and classify certain characteristics of objects and events, to divide them into groups based on common characteristics and signs. Children learn to think, draw conclusions, children's attention, memory and voluntary perception develop. The child explains his behavior when solving educational activities and game tasks. This helps to improve speech.

During educational activities and didactic games, children of different preschool ages consolidate the set of knowledge specific to the educational program of the kindergarten by repeating it many times. When choosing games to be played with natural materials, the educator should not forget that the content of the game corresponds to the changes in nature in the environment. For example: "Seed buying" game should be played in spring, and "Harvest" should be played in summer or autumn. The educator himself can think of various options for educational activities and games: an additional task to the game, educational activities, a new role, enriching children's knowledge of the surrounding nature, etc. Some of the same didactic games are recommended in different versions for children of different ages. Games become more complex due to the increase in the number of plants, animals or other objects, the increase in the number of different rules and game actions. For example: carrots, cucumbers, apples, etc. can be taken for palpation, and then fruits and vegetables of similar shape can be introduced.

Playing with leaves and flowers for children of preschool age is often associated with the desire to decorate the group room, dining table, and give bouquets and

leaves to adults and small children. When conducting such games and educational activities, it is necessary to teach children to be careful with plants and not to pluck flowers in vain. If the child focuses on the shape of an apple or other objects, it is necessary to offer him to roll the apple, stroke it like a ball, and determine its smoothness. Children should be taught to use the concepts of color, shape, and size. In the world of various natural phenomena, the most understandable for children to observe directly are plants and domestic animals. In the process of introducing children of preschool age to plants and animals, children are nurtured to love nature, and their desire to care for animals and grow plants is nurtured.

References:

1. Shamsheva A. Melibayeva R and others. University of General Psychology, 2016.
2. Безрукова В.С. Основы духовной культуры (энциклопедический словарь педагога) [Текст] / В.С. Безрукова. – Екатеринбург: ПЕРО, 2000. – 937 с.
3. Madraximovich, K. E., & Ruzimovich, Y. J. (2021). Application of Problem-Based Teaching Methods in the Development of Mathematical Thinking Skills of Students. *Annals of the Romanian Society for Cell Biology*, 43-47.
4. Khudoynazarov, E. (2023). THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF GROWING LOGICAL THINKING OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *International Bulletin of Engineering and Technology*, 3(5), 33-37.
5. Madrakhimovich, K. E. (2023). Didactic Principles of Developing Logical Thinking in Students. *New Scientific Trends and Challenges*, 97-100.
6. Худойназаров, Э. М., & Бекметова, З. З. Қ. (2022). ЎҚУВЧИЛАРДА ТАНҚИДИЙ ФИКРЛАШНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ПЕДАГОГИК ВА МЕТОДИК АСОСЛАРИ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(12), 1099-1107.
7. Эгамбергян, Х. М., & Хўжаниёзова, Ш. Б. (2023). АЛ-ХОРАЗМИЙ-БАРЧА ЗАМОНЛАРНИНГ ЭНГ УЛУҒ МАТЕМАТИГИ. *BOSHQARUV VA ETIKA QOIDALARI ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 3(1), 4-10.
8. Худойназаров, Э. М., & Авезова, Д. Ф. Қ. (2023). ИНСОН ФИКРЛАШНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ДИДАКТИК АСОСЛАРИ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(2), 310-317.
9. Худойназаров, Э. М., & Авезова, Д. Ф. Қ. (2023). ЎҚУВЧИЛАРДА МАНТИҚИЙ ФИКРЛАШНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ДИДАКТИК АСОСЛАРИ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(2), 289-297.

10. Сатлиқов, Ф. Р., & Худойназаров, Э. М. (2022). ЎҚУВЧИЛАРНИНГ ЎҚУВ-БИЛИШ ФАОЛЛИГИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШГА ТАЪСИР ЭТУВЧИ МУҲИМ ОМИЛЛАР. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(7), 800-805.
11. Мадрахимович, Э. Х., & Ражабова, С. М. (2022). ЭВРИСТИК МЕТОД ЁРДАМИДА БОШЛАНҒИЧ СИНФ ЎҚУВЧИЛАРИ ЎҚУВ ФАОЛЛИГИНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШ МЕТОДЛАРИ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 3(12), 315-323.
12. Худойназаров, Э. М., & Дўсчанова, М. М. (2022). БОШЛАНҒИЧ ТАЪЛИМДА ЎҚУВЧИЛАРДА ТАЯНЧ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЯЛАРНИ ШАКЛЛАНТИРИШНИНГ НАЗАРИЙ АСОСЛАРИ. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(12), 1108-1115.
13. Xudoynazarov, E. M., Xasanova, D. S. Q., & Rimboyev, N. M. Q. (2022). МАТЕМАТИК BOSHQOTIRMALAR–BOSHLANG ‘ICH TA’LIMDA O ‘QUVCHILAR O ‘QUV FAOLIYATINI OSHIRISH VOSITASI SIFATIDA. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(6), 174-181.
14. Худойназаров, Э. М. (2020). Устные упражнения как основа формирования и развития деятельности математического мышления у учащихся начальных классов. *International scientific review*, (LXXI), 93-94.
15. Худойназаров, Э. М., & Бобожонов, А. Б. СИНФДАН ТАШҚАРИ ИШЛАРДА ЎҚУВЧИЛАРИДА МАНТИҚИЙ ФИКРЛАШНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ИИНОВАЦИОН ЖИҲАТЛАРИ.
16. Худойназаров, Э. М. (2022). СИНФДАН ТАШҚАРИ ИШЛАР ЎҚУВЧИЛАР МАНТИҚИЙ ФИКРЛАШНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ОМИЛИ СИФАТИДА: <https://doi.org/10.53885/edinres.2022.8.08.032> Худойназаров Эгамберган Мадрахимович, катта ўқитувчи, Урганч давлат университети. Образование и инновационные исследования международный научно-методический журнал, (8), 207-211.